

IMPROVING THERAPEUTIC MEASURES FOR CHANGES IN THE ORAL MUCOSA AND TONGUE OF THE PATIENT IN A POSTOPERATIVE BARIATRIC CONDITION

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Abstract. *Bariatric surgery is the surgical repositioning of the stomach, intestines, or both for weight loss. Approximately 250,000 bariatric surgeries are performed in the United States each year. The development of safe laparoscopic techniques has made this operation more popular. To qualify for bariatric surgery, patients must have: body mass index (BMI) > 40 kg/m² or BMI > 35 kg/m² and serious complications (eg, diabetes, hypertension, obstructive sleep apnea, high risk factor blood lipid profile), an acceptable risk for surgery. Having tried all reasonable methods of non-surgical weight loss and successfully overcoming all complications from obesity. Bariatric surgery should also be considered for patients with type 2 diabetes, a BMI between 30 and 34.9, and glycemic control despite optimal lifestyle and drug therapy. Improving therapeutic measures for changes in the oral mucosa and tongue of a bariatric patient after surgery.*

Keywords: *Improvement of therapeutic measures for oral mucosal and tongue changes in postoperative bariatric patient is reported in detail.*

The development of dental pathologies, as a rule, is the result of the development of pathological processes occurring in the human body. Against the background of weakened immunity, the influence of external negative factors increases, which leads to the formation of problem areas. The causes of diseases can be different: the symptoms manifested in the tongue, lips and gums, as well as the results of clinical diagnostics, including professional equipment, can determine the source of concern. Classification of diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, correct diagnosis and timely initiation of therapy help to avoid more serious negative consequences.

Classification of diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity.

Stomatitis is an inflammation of the mucous membrane, characteristic of children and adults. Most often, stomatitis is bacterial, viral or fungal in nature. Bad toothbrushes with hard, scratchy bristles, improperly fitted braces or crowns, and biting of the cheeks and lips can also cause canker sores.

Most often, stomatitis manifests itself in the form of itchy, bright red or white sores and erosions on the inner surface of the cheek, tongue or gums. A person may complain of burning and swelling, bad breath, pain when chewing and swallowing. In severe cases, the temperature rises, sleep may be disturbed, and the person becomes nervous.

Glossitis is an inflammation of the tongue, which can occur as a result of injury (for example, burns), pathogens, or as a symptom of some systemic diseases. Often, glossitis is manifested by a burning sensation and discomfort in the mouth. The tongue is bright red, slightly

swollen, saliva may increase. The patient may complain of a loss of taste or a change in the sense of taste, eating or even just talking causes pain.

Cheilitis (or cheilosis) is a disease in which the lips begin to peel, break and "sticks" appear at the corners of the mouth. The reasons can be very different: exposure to wind and sun, allergic reaction, chronic diseases with skin lesions (dermatitis, psoriasis, etc.), endocrine pathologies or mycoses.

Oral leukoplakia

Oral leukoplakia is keratinization of the mucous membrane under the influence of aggressive factors such as smoking. This condition is considered precancerous and therefore requires mandatory treatment.

Often, oral leukoplakia appears as non-removable white, gray, or red plaques, rough or keratinized areas, or strange thickenings in the oral cavity. As a rule, the patient does not experience pain and discomfort, so he does not immediately consult a doctor.

Periodontosis

The periodontium is a complex of tissues that surrounds and supports the tooth: gums, periodontal ligament, periodontium, root cementum and bone tissue. Periodontal diseases include: gingivitis, periodontitis and periodontal disease.

Gingivitis

Gingivitis is an inflammation of the gums caused by improper or improper oral hygiene. Pathogens accumulate in plaque and tartar, causing inflammation.

Inflammation with gingivitis affects only the surface of the gums and can cause bleeding, swelling of the gums, mild pain or discomfort when pressed, and bad breath. If treatment is not started, the inflammation will increase and affect the periodontium.

Periodontitis and periodontal disease

Often, patients confuse periodontitis and periodontal disease. Periodontitis is an inflammatory disease of the periodontal tissues, which causes the gums to bleed and gradually affects the roots of the teeth, their mobility and, as a result, their loss. Periodontal disease is a non-inflammatory periodontal disease in which the mucous membrane of the gums and jawbone is gradually reduced. Unlike periodontitis, which destroys tooth tissue over several years, periodontal disease develops very slowly and develops over decades. The patient may not even realize that he has gum disease. Periodontal disease is rare compared to other oral diseases. Damage to the tissues of the oral cavity and other traumatic effects (chemical, thermal, etc.) with the development of traumatic erosion, ulcers, leukoplakia or leukokeratosis. Infectious diseases affecting the mucous membrane of the oral cavity due to the penetration of viruses, spirochetes, bacteria and fungi. Most often, the appearance of pathological changes in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity is associated with disorders of various organs and systems of the body: allergies, cardiovascular system, gastrointestinal tract, endocrine diseases, systemic connective tissue diseases, blood diseases and other dermatoses, tuberculosis, AIDS and some other conditions.

Diagnosis of pathologies

Modern methods used in dentistry allow to quickly identify infectious or fungal diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. It is worth noting that self-diagnosis, as well as subsequent attempts at self-treatment, often lead to a worsening of the general condition. Determining the causes of pathological changes is a medical task, for which the following are used:

- Microscopic examination of samples.
- Test for allergic reactions.
- Test for viral pathogens.
- General examination and medical history.

It is necessary to make a timely diagnosis in order to develop and implement the correct treatment plan that takes into account the negative symptoms and factors that cause pathological changes. Principles of treatment of diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. The main principles of treatment of diseases of the mucous membranes of the mouth, lips and tongue. Rational treatment requires communication between the dentist and other dental and non-dental professionals. Treatment should be carried out in accordance with the principles of bioethics, these diseases should be considered from the point of view of the state of the whole organism, so in many cases it is impossible to limit oneself only to local effects.

The axiom for the dentist should be to eliminate all unpleasant irritating factors that help and provoke the development of the pathological process in the patient's oral cavity. It is impossible to use cauterizing agents and to use the same mouthwashes for a long time. Treatment should begin only after at least one preliminary diagnosis has been made and the following requirements have been met: be comprehensive; providing a pathogenetic approach; do not violate the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the oral mucosa; eliminate the pain factor; stimulation of rapid epithelization of lesions; to ensure the active participation of the patient in conducting treatment procedures at home.

Therapy methods

Etiotropic and pathogenetic therapy aimed at eliminating the cause of the disease (due to the infectious nature of stomatitis, glossitis, cheilitis, antiviral, antibacterial therapy, vitamin therapy for hypovitaminosis, treatment of the main disease that led to the appearance of the pathological process in the oral cavity). cavity of the mucous membrane;

Local treatment aimed at eliminating local traumatic factors, the main symptoms of the disease and faster healing of existing erosion and wounds;

A general strengthening procedure that stimulates the body's defenses.

To prevent painful symptoms, experts recommend following the universal rules of oral hygiene:

- a) use correctly selected toothbrushes, use them regularly, and also avoid bad habits, especially smoking.
- b) It is recommended to monitor your diet: in some cases, irritation of the oral cavity can be caused by excessive consumption of oranges, lemons, etc.
- c) the habit of cleaning the seeds with the teeth rather than with the hands can be uncomfortable for the oral cavity.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, improving therapeutic measures for changes in the oral mucosa and tongue of patients in a postoperative bariatric condition requires a comprehensive and collaborative approach.

By focusing on patient education, regular monitoring, and preventive measures, healthcare professionals can help these individuals maintain optimal oral health and improve their overall postoperative experience.

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